

GAD PROJECT: GAME CREATION IN AUGMENTED REALITY (AR) ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL DIGITAL SKILLS – AN OPPORTUNITY TO SUPPORT TEACHING IN TECHNICAL DISCIPLINES

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Abstract

The GAD Game project is promoted by the European Commission through the small-scale association's Erasmus+ Program (2021-1-IT01-KA210-VET-000034522) and has a double objective (*i*) to develop a free and versatile AR application for the teaching of technical studies; and (*ii*) accompany the teaching-learning process with a methodological approach of the trainers based on the principles of gamification, to achieve a successful application in the classroom. GAD Game thus addresses the development of educators' digcomps and the ability to create digital learning environments and educational products suitable to meet new training challenges. In this communication, the objectives, methodology and preliminary results of the project are presented. In particular, the development of a free APP for Android and iOS systems and the creation of case interactive lessons based on three-dimension (3D) models in the areas of Engineering, Biology and Health are shown.

Keywords: Augmented reality, digital skills, gamification, app.

1 INTRODUCTION

The teaching of technical studies is traditionally supported by the use of two-dimensional views for the schematic representation of complex elements. The geometric pieces are normally represented in their elevation or plane views, and only in specific technical drawing subjects are the three views used. The appearance of three-dimension (3D)-based technologies such as 3D printing is promoting both training and communication through 3D elements, as well as the digital competence of teachers about 3D design. A step towards the future is represented by augmented reality (AR) and/or virtual reality (VR), which uses computer-generated 3D scenes and objects that appear to be real. It is very likely that, in a few years, teachers will use AR to represent elements such as reactors, heat exchangers, treatment plants, rectification towers and other elements of the industry. This will allow much more direct, attractive and significant learning for technical education students.

In this sense, the European Commission has deployed the Digital Education Action Plan [1], which highlights the need to constantly update the digital skills of teachers/tutors/trainers to improve their professional performance and increase the level of student participation. There are two strategic priorities: the development of a high-performing digital education ecosystem and the enhancement of digital skills and competencies. The need to boost advanced digital skills is evident in national educational programs that aim to develop the digital skills of teachers (i.e., digcomps) [2], especially after the post-pandemic social reorganization, but only a few use augmented reality. Despite its popularity in marketing, entertainment, and school education, this technology is very rare in secondary and higher education. While AR games for educational purposes exist, they are generally not free and cannot be developed further.

The GAD project [3], funded under the Erasmus+ program, was born as a response to the European need to qualify the digital skills of educational and professional organizations through the creation of a tool that will allow teachers, tutors and educators to innovate their teaching practices by integrating technology, and more specifically augmented reality. The consortium of the GAD project, summarised in Fig. 1, is composed of: (*i*) Paidea, an Italian organisation that consults, produces and motivates educations process through technology; (*ii*) Universitat de València, a Spanish university striving for

innovation, research and qualitative education; and (iii) Dafni Kek, a Greek adult education and research centre that strives for access in adult learning.

Figure 1. GAD Project consortium.

The GAD Game, the main result of the GAD Project, is the response to the above-mentioned needs. By including the GAD Game in the educational practice, educators can offer access to existing but not widely accessible settings and equipment, visualise historical artefacts and abstract concepts, or showcase the constituent parts of a complex organism. All of these are through the use and development of 3D models.

The GAD Project addresses educators, teachers and tutors, which are the main target of the project, since the main objective concerns the increase of their digital skills concerning the engagement of the students and providing incentives to participate, collaborate and learn to create and be creative. Also, educational institutions play an important role in supporting and inspiring educators to increase their skills, by offering quality training, adequate infrastructure and actual incentives and guarantees that educators feel supported and respected in their work. Finally, students are those to indirectly assess the process but also those who better reflect the progress. Their contribution to the research is crucial to help understand the extent of the importance of the use of such technologies in the educational process, as well as measure their level of participation compared to the more traditional modes.

Among the benefits of the GAD Project in education, it must be highlighted that no special equipment is required. Unlike VR, augmented reality doesn't require any expensive hardware. Because most European learners currently own a smartphone or a tablet, AR technologies are immediately available for use for the majority of the target audience. Moreover, it improves collaboration capabilities. AR offers vast opportunities to diversify and shake up boring classes. Interactive lessons, where all students are involved in the learning process at the same time, help improve teamwork skills. It also promotes practical learning. Apart from schooling, professional training can also benefit greatly from the use of AR, being safe and efficient workplace training. Finally, it is universally applicable to any level of education and training. Be it learning games for kindergarten or on-the-job training, AR isn't limited to only one-use case or field of application [4].

The GAD Game is based on the psychological and educational value of gamification. It uses a digital game to increase students' motivation to learn. By mixing gamification and digital learning it aims to foster users' interest and engagement to make them change their behaviour. Particularly, GAD Game intends to foster the following digcomps: (i) developing, integrating and re-elaborating digital content + developing digital effective learning modes; (ii) actively involving students in shaping the learning process; and (iii) responsibly using digital technologies for problem-solving [5].

The results achieved by GAD Game will additionally impact the local community which will receive all the necessary information to participate and will be informed on the project; and the European community because the outputs will be openly accessible to everyone for free, as well as the dissemination activities.

2 METHODOLOGY

GAD Game is a digital learning game based on augmented reality, developed through the active contribution of teachers. During the development of the GAD Game, teachers improve their digital skills, understand the game logic and learn how to use it. The game runs both on a platform and on its app. The GAD Platform [6] allows to create lessons, share their own 3D creations and see the progress of the students. The GAD Game app for smartphones has been implemented on both Android and iOS, which features a series of 3D models used in the educational process by interacting with the learning environment. Each model is followed by a small quiz based on the example lessons created by the professionals that were participating in the project workshops.

During the development of the GAD Game, the partners implemented a series of workshops for educators. These workshops aimed at enhancing the professional's digital skills, by using, editing and recreating their own 3D models. The training material used was focused on the uses of 3D models in education and how they help support experiential learning and act as motivational strategies for students to learn and develop also their skills.

3 RESULTS

3.1 GAD Game workshops

The target group of this activity were teachers/tutors/educators that had an active role in the prototyping of the Game as an educational tool. The workshops started in June and were completed in October of 2022, with the participation of 12 educators and relevant professionals from Italy, Spain and Greece. They were implemented both online and face-to-face and each group participated in a total of 5 sessions, both theoretical and hands-on. The educational material used and developed during the workshops, was reviewed and uploaded for public access on the project's website leading up to the date of the final conference of the GAD project.

The first workshops started in Italy, Spain and Greece (6 total), involving the beginning of the research, in June 2022. The next phase of the workshops (6 total) dealt with testing the app in relation to other apps, models on the platform and educational frameworks, between July and August 2022. The final phase of workshops in September 2022 (6 total) consisted of the last phase of research together with the definition of content for the platform. Lastly, interviews with educators and students during October 2022 allowed for public piloting of the platform and the app. In December 2022, the project's partners, the professionals that participated in the workshops and other stakeholders and interested individuals, got together in an online launch event to share their experiences of the GAD Game and project overall. The event was a really rewarding experience and it highlighted all the different approaches and diverse needs that were addressed with the use of the GAD Game and AR in general.

3.2 GAD Game platform

The platform is a repository where educators can upload their creations, preview and download them for editing other educators' models as well as exchange information. It allows the creation of personal accounts for gathering the work in a given profile. The platform permits saving and editing existing 3D models sharing of models, as well as sharing content and creating tests.

These models can be obtained from 3D-file repositories such as Sketchfab [7], which is one of the leading platforms for 3D and AR on the web. As an example, Fig. 3 shows a heat exchanger from Sketchfab, which can be applied in the context of several engineering disciplines.

Figure 2. Heat exchanger 3D model from Sketchfab.

For the creation of a lesson, following a chronological order, the first step is to choose the subject. Afterwards, one chooses the topic to explore, the second step is to create the 3D models, which will be subsequently included in the lesson during the third step. One will be asked to provide a title for the lesson, a short description of the educational goals, name role and finally upload the 3D model. Finally, the fourth step involves the creation of a quiz for the student's evaluation. Reviewing how and what students learnt is an essential element of practice and effectiveness. This sequence can be visually appreciated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. GAD platform screenshots.

Complementarily, lessons created by other teachers are stored in an existing lessons repository. There, one can find multiple already created lessons and quizzes, categorized and organized for easier use. The content is currently classified according to the categories of art, science, engineering and health.

3.3 GAD Game app

The GAD App is based on the psychological and educational value of gamification. It uses a digital game to increase students' motivation to learn. By mixing gamification and digital learning it aims to foster users' interest and engagement to make them change their behaviour.

The app is available at the PlayStore [8] and can be used by both educators and students. The educator can import and control the model, and share it with the students who can interact with it two and more persons at a time. The viewing of the model is followed by a simple examination. During model viewing, the user can manipulate the object, rotate the view around and zoom in and out the model.

The app allows for simultaneous view and interaction, with accurate guidance along the different screens, with the possibility of evaluating students' knowledge and offering the possibility of offline access. Fig. 4 shows some of the screenshots of the different steps during the use of the app, where a chemical molecule and a heat exchanger can be appreciated.

Figure 4. GADGame app in the PlayStore together with some screenshots of its use.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The key outcomes of the GAD Project are that the platform and the app have a high transferability potential, as they can be used by other teachers/ tutors/ educators. As well, through the platform, it will be possible to develop different types of open-source educational content, according to the student's needs. Through learning by doing, trainers will develop several digcomps (levels 2, 3, 5, 6 DigCompEdu) and will be able to add their educational content and tailor it to their specific targets.

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